

The role of the endothelial dysfunction at vibration disease.

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Abstract. We present data upon the blood vessels of endothelium, on the basis of the eicosanoid metabolism research at patients with vibration disease. According to the obtained data an imbalance of vasodilators and vasoconstrictors at patients already with the initial manifestations of vibration disease was educed.

Key words: vibration disease, endothelial dysfunction, eicosanoids, leukotrienes, prostaglandins.

The local vibration has still remained a harmful factor of the production in many industries [1, 3, 4]. Its effect on the body of a worker sets off the compensatory and adaptive complex of mechanisms and causes a variety of changes of all organs and systems [6]. In the pathogenesis of vibration disease (WB), the endothelial dysfunction (ED) or a violation of the functional state of the vessels of endothelium plays a significant role [7, 8]. The leading role in the mechanism of ED plays the oxidative stress, an output of powerful vasoconstrictors that suppress the NO production. At prolonged impact of the damaging factors: hemodynamic overload, hypoxia, inflammations which are peculiar to workers with vibrating tools, depletion and distortion of endothelial function take place, and response to normal stimuli are vasoconstriction, proliferation of the elements of the vascular wall and thrombus formation [9]. Eicosanoids are actively involved in the regulation of vascular tone system, many of them are actively synthesized directly in the vascular wall of endothelium. The viscosity of the blood, its rheological properties, the condition of vascular tone are largely determined by the level of prostaglandins and leukotrienes in blood. At normal conditions, the output of vasoconstrictors and vasodilators is in equilibrium [1].

The aim of the study was to examine the state of the blood vessels of endothelium, based on the study exchange of eicosanoids at patients with vibration disease.

Materials and methods. Clinical base for the research was the Research Institute of Labour Hygiene and Occupational Diseases of Kharkiv National Medical University.

The study included 107 patients with the vibration disease diagnosis from the effects of local vibration I and II degree, aged 41 to 66 years (mean age $(54 \pm 6,17)$ years). The content of leukotrienes and prostaglandins in the serum was determined by analysis using radioimmuno diagnostic test systems «Amersham» (United Kingdom). Statistical analysis of data was performed using a computer package of applied programmes for statistical information processing Statistica 6.1 (StatSoft, Inc., USA), to compare two normal distributions was used the Student's t-test. If at least one of the distribution was not normal, then to compare independent samples the Manna-rank test was applied.

Results and discussion. In order to assess ED at patients with vibration disease, we conducted the research of biochemical blood content of eicosanoids. There was a significant increase in LTV4-49,9 pg / ml ME [46,12; 55.12] against 25.71 pg / ml ME [20,68; 28.09] in the control group of examined people. The content of LTS4 almost unchanged at the patients with VD. There was a significant increase in the content of the prostaglandin compared to the control: PGE2-2154 pg / ml ME [1836; 2428] versus 1649 pg / ml ME [1211; 1867] PGF2 α - 26.10 pg / ml ME [23,20; 29.14] versus 16.9 pg / ml ME [14,33; 19,20] ($p < 0.05$).

Thus, the development of the vibration disease is combined with the formation of endothelial dysfunction and is characterized by an increase of the synthesis of the vasodilatory factors by the endothelium vessels. The violation of the synthesis of vasodilators leads to the uncompensated synthesis of constrictors and significantly increases the risk of vasospastic reactions, contributes to the progression of vascular pathology with the development of angiosclerosis [2]. It is also known that they are involved in redox processes, have antiplatelet effect, slow pathological proliferative processes, prevent the interaction of endothelium and leukocytes, counteract the decrement of blood flow due to mechanical or thrombotic occlusion of blood vessels, inhibit lipid peroxidation [10]. In turn, the endothelial vasoconstrictors activate free radical oxidation, promote the adhesion and aggregation of platelets and leukocytes on the endothelial surface, contribute microcirculation disorder and thrombus formation [5].

Conclusions. The analysis of the research results showed the presence of chronic inflammation at VD, which confirms the high level of LTB4 in the group of patients with VD. Also, the obtained data indicate that activation of prostaglandin synthesis at VD takes place. There has been already found an increase in all groups of prostaglandins: prostaglandin PGF2 α level of pressor and depressor prostaglandin PGE2. Such changes are typical for the angiospastic syndrome, which is shown in most patients early during the vibration disease. The predominance of the prostaglandins changes over the

leukotrienes ones shows the involvement of prostaglandins in the implementation of vascular reactions and hemodynamic disorders at vibration disease, and the presence of vasodilation on the early stages of vibration disease. So, one of the pathogenetic links of vibration disease development is endothelial dysfunction, as indicated by the imbalance between substances produced in the endothelium, which are responsible for contraction and expansion of blood vessels. The violation of eicosanoids synthesis, particularly prostaglandins in the vascular wall is leading to the development of endothelial dysfunction, and the last one, to a greater extent, causes a change in the status of eicosanoid.

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